

1 **Comparative study of fetal and carcinoembryonic antigens for ECT2-type labeling or identification**
2 **of transformed tissues.**

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7 We discuss uses for and challenges associated with use of different tumor antigens for diagnosis and
8 prevention, including Tacstd2 (Trop-2), Tpbg, CA family carbonic anhydrase enzymes, and ECT2.

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10 Citations

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